

Interview Guide

Table 1, Interview guide for Testers and Developers

Interview question code (td = test and developer)	Interview question
tdQ1	How long (years and months) have you worked at this organization?
tdQ2	What characteristics/attributes do you perceive a good requirement to have?
tdQ3	Please describe the process when you work with a user story that you perceive to be good, from receiving the user story until it is considered done?
tdQ4	What characteristics/attributes do you perceive a bad requirement to have, or what characteristics/attributes does it lack?
tdQ5	Please describe the process when you work with a user story that you perceive to be bad, from receiving the user story until it is considered done?
tdQ5a	How do bad requirements impact your work?
tdQ5b	How do you overcome the challenges you experience with bad requirements?
tdQ5c	What words would you use to describe how it feels to work with bad requirements?
tdQ5d	How much longer in time, on average, would you estimate that it takes to finish a user story that you perceive to be bad?
tdQ5e	How have you experienced bad requirements to affect the product in terms of quality or time to release?
tdQ6	What differences have you observed in team communication depending on the perceived quality of requirements?
tdQ7	How often, in percent, do you experience that a story that has been sent to the testers is either sent back to the requirements engineers or the developers?
tdQ7a	How often, in percent, do you perceive that user stories that are sent back to developers, or requirements engineers, have had “bad” requirements?
tdQ8	How challenging would you rate testing with the requirements at this organization to be? (1-10, 1 is very easy, 5-6 is moderate, and 10 is very difficult)
tdQ8a	What is your reasoning for that number?
tdQ9	Would you like to add anything to this interview?

Table 2, Interview guide for Requirements Engineers

Interview question code (re=requirement engineer)	Interview question
reQ1	How long (years and months) have you worked at this organization?
reQ2	What training do you have in requirement engineering? (School, courses, in-house documents, etc.)
reQ3	What characteristics/attributes do you perceive a good requirement to have?
reQ4	What are this organization's norms for a good requirement?
reQ4a	Do you think that the norms are good enough to achieve objectively good quality?
reQ4b	How have you been informed of the norms?
reQ5	Please describe your work process when you are creating a requirement for a user story?
reQ6	What challenges do you experience when creating requirements at this organization?
reQ6a	How do the challenges that you experience when creating requirements impact your work?
reQ6b	How do you overcome the challenges that you experience when creating requirements?
reQ6c	What words would you use to describe how it makes you feel to work with creating requirements?
reQ6d	How much longer in time, on average, would you estimate that challenging requirements take for you to produce?
reQ7	How often, in percent, do you experience that you have created a requirement that you consider is non-optimal?
reQ7a	How often have you felt forced to release requirements that you have created that do not fulfill your definition of a good requirement or the norms of this organization?
reQ7b	How have you identified that some requirements do not fulfill your definition of a good requirement or the norms of this organization?
reQ7c	What do you think could be the causes of the bad requirements that you have produced?
reQ7d	How do you perceive requirements of different quality to affect the development and testing?
reQ7e	What generally happens when developers or testers perceive one of your requirements as a non-optimal requirement?
reQ7f	How do bad requirements that you have produced affect your work?
reQ8	Do you experience any difference with how many questions developers or testers ask about a user story when they are new in the organization or team compared to if they have worked at least a few sprints in the team?

reQ9	What do you think could realistically be done to remove the constraints or challenges you experience when creating requirements?
reQ10	How challenging would you rate creating the requirements at this organization to be? (1-10, 1 is very easy, 5-6 is moderate, and 10 is very difficult)
reQ10a	What is your reasoning for that number?
reQ11	Would you like to add anything to this interview?

Table 3, Interview guides for Newly employed Developers

Interview question code (new1=newly employed developer, first interview)	Interview question
new1Q1	How long have you worked at your consultant firm (years, months/weeks)?
new1Q2	How long have you been assigned to work with this organization (years, months/weeks)?
new1Q3	How many years of experience did you have in software development before being assigned to this organization?
new1Q3a	If you can reveal it, what companies have you worked with before?
new1Q4	What characteristics/attributes do you perceive a good requirement to have?
new1Q5	Please describe the process when you work with a user story that you perceive to be good, from receiving the user story until it is considered done?
new1Q6	What characteristics/attributes do you perceive a bad requirement to have, or what characteristics/attributes does it lack?
new1Q7	Out of all requirements you have worked with at this organization, how many do you estimate, in percent, have been bad requirements?
new1Q7a	Please describe the process when you work with a user story that you perceive to be bad, from receiving the user story until it is considered done?
new1Q7b	What words would you use to describe how it feels to work with bad requirements?
new1Q7c	How much longer in time, on average, would you estimate that it takes to finish a user story that you perceive to be bad
new1Q8	What challenges do you experience when working with requirements at this organization compared to what you have experienced in earlier assignments? (i.e., in other companies)
new1Q8a	What challenges have you experienced at this organization that you have also experienced with earlier assignments?
new1Q8b	What do you do to overcome the challenges that you experience when working with requirements at this organization?
new1Q9	What impacts do the challenges you have experienced with requirements at this organization have on your work?
new1Q9a	On average, how much longer would you estimate that it takes to finish a user story with the challenges you experience?
new1Q10	How challenging would you rate working with the requirements at this organization to be? (1-10, 1 is very easy, 5-6 is moderate, and 10 is very difficult)
new1Q10a	What is your reasoning for that number?
new1Q11	Would you like to add anything to this interview?
Interview question code	Interview question

(new2=newly employed developer, second interview)	
new2Q1	How long have you been assigned to work with this organization?
new2Q2	What characteristics or attributes do you perceive a good requirement to have?
new2Q3	What characteristics/attributes do you perceive a bad requirement to have, or what characteristics/attributes does it lack?
new2Q4	Out of all requirements you have worked with at this organization, how many do you estimate, in percent, were bad requirements?
new2Q4a	Please describe the process when you work with a user story that you perceive to be bad, from receiving the user story until it is considered done?
new2Q4b	What words would you use to describe how it feels to work with bad requirements?
new2Q4c	How much longer in time, on average, would you estimate that it takes to finish a user story that you perceive to be bad?
new2Q5	What challenges have you experienced with working with requirements at this organization since the last interview?
new2Q5a	What challenges have you not experienced since the last interview?
new2Q6	What impacts do the challenges you have experienced with requirements at this organization have on your work?
new2Q6a	What do you do to overcome the challenges that you experience when working with requirements at this organization?
new2Q6b	On average, how much longer would you estimate that it takes to finish a user story with the challenges you experience?
new2Q7	How challenging would you rate working with the requirements at this organization to be? (1-10, 1 is very easy, 5-6 is moderate, and 10 is very difficult)
new2Q7a	What is your reasoning for that number?
new2Q8	Would you like to add anything to this interview?